

****SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES and TABLES****

Splenic Modulation of the Early Inflammatory Response to Regional and Global Ischemia/Reperfusion Injury in Swine

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Short Title: Splenic Modulation of Post-Ischemic Inflammation

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ELISA Kit	Vendor	Catalog #	Target (Species)
cTnl	Life Diagnostics	CTNI-9-US	Porcine
IL-6	R&D Systems	P6000B	Porcine
TNF α	R&D Systems	PTA00	Porcine

Table S1: ELISA Kits

Antibody	Vendor	Catalog #	Dilution
Fc Block	Miltenyi Biotec	130-059-901	2.5ug/1e6 cells
7AAD	Invitrogen	00-6993-50	0.25ug/1e6 cells
αlgG1 (FITC)	Bio-rad	MCA928F	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αlgG1 (PE)	Bio-rad	MCA928PE	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αlgG2a (PE)	R&D Systems	IC003P	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αlgG2b (FITC)	Bio-rad	MCA691F	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αCD45 (PB)	Bio-rad	MCA1222PB	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αCD172 (FITC)	BD Biosciences	561498	0.5ug/1e6 cells
αCD163 (PE)	Bio-rad	MCA2311PE	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αCD14 (FITC)	Bio-rad	MCA1218F	0.25uL/1e6 cells
αCD16 (PE)	Bio-rad	MCA1971PE	0.25uL/1e6 cells

Table S2: Flow Cytometry Antibodies

Gating Strategy

Figure S1. Flow Cytometry Gating Strategy. Top) Representative utilization of control samples to place quadrant gates. Bottom) Representative implementation of gating strategy on experimental samples.

Figure S2. Circulating and Tissue Inflammatory Markers Following AMI. Percent change (%) of CBC cell count from Pre-AMI of circulating A) WBCs, B) monocytes, C) platelets, D) neutrophils, E) lymphocytes and F) neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio at 1hr Post-AMI, and 4hr Post-AMI in SHAM (purple) and SPLX (light blue) animals. Data represents AVE \pm SD. n = 6-SHAM, 6-SPLX. *p < 0.05 vs SHAM. #p < 0.05 vs Pre-AMI.

FLOW - *Heart*

Figure S3. AMI vs. SCA Flow Cytometry of Cardiac Infiltration at Necropsy. Flow cytometry (%CD45+7AAD-) of Anterior LV and Posterior LV levels of A) inflammatory granulocytes (CD172+CD163-), B) inflammatory dendritic cells (CD172+CD16+), and C) inflammatory macrophages (CD14+CD163+) in normal control (teal), SHAM - AMI (purple), SPLX - AMI (light blue), SHAM - SCA (orange), SPLX - SCA (red) animals. Data represents AVE \pm SD. n = 6, 6, 6, 4, 4. \$p < 0.05 vs Normal Control. \$\$0.05 < p < 0.1 vs Normal Control.

Linear Regression Time to ROSC vs cTnI A.U.C.

Figure S4. Linear Regression of cTnI AUC and Time to ROSC. cTnI AUC was calculated by trapezoid method from Pre-SCA through 4-hour post-ROSC, while time to ROSC was recorded in seconds from initiation of CPR. SPLX, Splenectomy. Line of best fit was calculated to determine R_2 value, p-value (slope), and p-value vs SHAM (slope).

Figure S5. Circulating and Tissue Inflammatory Markers Following SCA. Percent change (%) of CBC cell count from Pre-SCA of circulating A) WBCs, B) monocytes, C) platelets, D) neutrophils, E) lymphocytes and F) neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio at 10min Post-ROSC, 1hr Post-ROSC, and 4hr Post-ROSC in SHAM (purple) and SPLX (light blue) animals. Data represents AVE ± SD. n = 4-SHAM, 4-SPLX. *p < 0.05 vs SHAM. #p < 0.05 vs Pre-SCA

<i>Blood Gas Data</i>	SHAM (n=9)	SPLX (n=9)	p-value (Sham vs. Splx)
Baseline			
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	8.5 ± 0.6	9.5 ± 0.9*	0.02
Hematocrit (%)	25.6 ± 1.2	28.4 ± 3.0*	0.02
SaO ₂ (%)	99.1 ± 0.6	98.8 ± 0.9	0.40
O ₂ Content (mL/dL)	11.5 ± 0.6	12.7 ± 1.2*	0.02
Red Blood Cells (10 ⁶ /μL)	6.2 ± 0.3	6.8 ± 0.6*	0.02
2-min CPR			
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	12.0 ± 1.2	10.0 ± 1.2*	<0.01
Hematocrit (%)	36.1 ± 3.9	30.2 ± 3.0*	<0.01
SaO ₂ (%)	91.7 ± 4.8	87.2 ± 14.4	0.47
O ₂ Content (mL/dL)	14.9 ± 1.5	11.9 ± 2.1*	<0.01
10-min post-ROSC (n=4/group)			
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	12.2 ± 0.6	10.4 ± 0.6*	0.01
Hematocrit (%)	36.4 ± 1.8	31.2 ± 1.8*	0.01
SaO ₂ (%)	87.8 ± 14.2	88.4 ± 19.0	0.96
O ₂ Content (mL/dL)	14.1 ± 2.2	12.4 ± 2.4	0.33
Red Blood Cells (10 ⁶ /μL)	7.8 ± 0.4	6.9 ± 0.6*	0.03
1-hour post-ROSC (n=4/group)			
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	11.0 ± 0.8	9.2 ± 0.2*	<0.01
Hematocrit (%)	32.9 ± 2.2	27.7 ± 5.6*	<0.01
SaO ₂ (%)	97.6 ± 1.0	98.6 ± 0.2	0.13
O ₂ Content (mL/dL)	14.5 ± 1.2	12.4 ± 0.2*	0.01
Red Blood Cells (10 ⁶ /μL)	7.3 ± 0.4	6.4 ± 0.2*	0.01
4-hour post-ROSC (n=4/group)			
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	7.3 ± 0.2	8.2 ± 0.6*	0.05
Hematocrit (%)	22.0 ± 0.6	24.6 ± 1.4*	0.04
SaO ₂ (%)	97.9 ± 0.4	98.6 ± 0.4*	0.07
O ₂ Content (mL/dL)	9.8 ± 0.4	11.0 ± 0.8*	0.04
Red Blood Cells (10 ⁶ /μL)	5.7 ± 0.2	5.9 ± 0.4*	0.02

Table S3. Raw Data from Arterial Blood Gas Before, During, and After SCA. Arterial blood gas values are presented as AVE ± SD. SPLX, Splenectomy; SCA, Sudden Cardiac Arrest. *p < 0.05 vs SHAM, highlighted, represents two-tailed Student's t-test.